

GGOS Strategic Plan 2024 – 2034

Geodesy for Science and Society

November 2023

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Strategic Planning Committee

Laura Sánchez

Technische Universität München, Deutsches
Geodätisches Forschungsinstitut (DGFI-TUM)
Munich, Germany

Basara Miyahara

Geospatial Information Authority,
Tsukuba, Japan

Allison B. Craddock

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute
of Technology, Pasadena, USA

Martin Sehnal

Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying,
Vienna, Austria

Detlef Angermann

Technische Universität München, Deutsches
Geodätisches Forschungsinstitut (DGFI-TUM),
Munich, Germany

Richard Gross

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute
of Technology, Pasadena, USA

Harald Schuh

Helmholtz Centre Potsdam
GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences,
Potsdam, Germany

Layout and Graphics

Laura Sánchez, Martin Sehnal

Photography

Pexels, Tobias Bjørkli (p. 3)

Pexels, Erik Téllez (p. 3)

Pexels, Jeremy Bishop (p. 3)

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Contact Information

GGOS Coordinating Office
Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying
Schiffamtsgasse 1-3, 1020 Vienna, Austria

www.ggos.org | co@ggos.org

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Acronyms

CARE	Collective benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reuse
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GGOS	Global Geodetic Observing System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
GRACE	Gravity Recovery And Climate Experiment
IAG	International Association of Geodesy
ICC	Inter-Commission Committees
InSAR	Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar
MAGIC	Mass-Change and Geosciences International Constellation
SAR	Synthetic-Aperture Radar
SCoG	Sub-Committee on Geodesy
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology
UN	United Nations
UN-GGCE	United Nations Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence
UN-GGIM	United Nations Committee of Experts on Global Geospatial Information Management
UN-GGRF	United Nations Global Geodetic Reference Frame

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Foreword

GGOS's Strategic Plan resonates profoundly with core principles of the International Association of Geodesy. It aligns seamlessly with our mission to promote and advance the understanding of Earth's shape, gravity field, and geodynamic phenomena, ensuring that our efforts remain at the forefront of scientific discovery.

R. Gross, Z. Altamimi

The International Association of Geodesy (IAG) takes great pride in welcoming the Global Geodetic Observing System's (GGOS) new Strategic Plan. Geodesy, the science of measuring and understanding Earth's shape, gravity field, and rotation, stands as a cornerstone of our efforts to comprehend the intricate dynamics of our planet. In this pursuit, GGOS has established itself as a beacon of integration, fostering international collaboration and driving innovation to new horizons. As the incoming and outgoing Presidents of the IAG, we are elated to highlight the importance of the new GGOS Strategic Plan, which not only underscores the significance of geodetic observations and products but also outlines a visionary roadmap for our collective endeavours.

The challenges we face in the 21st century transcend borders and disciplines. The impacts of climate change, urbanisation, natural disasters, and the need for sustainable resource management compel us to seek holistic solutions grounded in accurate geodetic data. GGOS's Strategic Plan, meticulously crafted with input from experts across the IAG Components and around the globe, not only reaffirms our commitment to addressing these challenges but also paves the way for innovative approaches that will drive progress across a multitude of sectors.

Throughout the Strategic Plan, GGOS is dedicated to the overall benefit of the IAG. Goal 1 aims to elevate geodesy's significance in global endeavours, showcasing its role in monitoring the Earth system, enhancing disaster readiness, promoting sustainability, and encouraging interdisciplinary teamwork. Goal 2 emphasises aligning geodetic science with policy-making, spotlighting practical geodetic applications, and involving the geodesy community in global policy conversations. Goal 3 concentrates on boosting geodetic know-how and infrastructure, fostering innovation, supporting data initiatives and infrastructure enhancements, and cultivating global collaboration among geodesists. The overarching objective is to optimise the value of geodetic data for worldwide initiatives and societal welfare.

Goal 4 centres on advancing geodetic research by encouraging multidisciplinary cooperation, standardisation of data analysis, and integration of geodetic products. By merging geodetic insights and skills, GGOS aims to provide precise, dependable, and easily accessible information that aids decision-making, scientific research, and improved comprehension of Earth's changes.

Through enhanced collaboration, cutting-edge technology, and a renewed emphasis on outreach, GGOS's Strategic Plan resonates profoundly with IAG's core principles. It aligns seamlessly with our mission to promote and advance the understanding of Earth's shape, gravity field, and geodynamic phenomena, ensuring that our efforts remain at the forefront of scientific discovery.

As we embark on this transformative journey, let us remember that our strength lies in the unity of our Association. The International Association of Geodesy stands firmly behind GGOS's Strategic Plan, recognising it as a great opportunity to shape the future of geodetic science. Together, we shall amplify our impact, redefine the boundaries of knowledge, and propel global geodesy to new heights.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to each of you for your unwavering dedication to our science and our chosen profession, and we invite you to join us in embracing this new chapter of geodetic excellence. The future is bright, and together, we shall illuminate the path ahead.

Richard Gross
IAG President 2023 – 2027
Jet Propulsion Laboratory,
California Institute of Technology,
Pasadena, USA

Zuheir Altamimi
IAG President 2019 – 2023
Institut National de l'Information
Géographique et Forestière and
Institut de Physique du Globe de
Paris, Paris, France

Executive Summary

Our Strategic Plan encompasses an ambitious vision, one that envisions a future where geodetic data is not a scientific asset only, but an essential resource guiding decision-making across diverse fields. From monitoring the Earth system and mitigating the impacts of climate change to bolstering disaster resilience and underpinning sustainable development, the power of geodetic observations and products knows no bounds.

L. Sánchez, B. Miyahara

As the world evolves at an unprecedented pace, our commitment to understanding the dynamic interplay between the Earth and its various components remains steadfast. With an unwavering dedication to advancing global geodetic knowledge, we proudly present the new Strategic Plan of the International Association of Geodesy's Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS). The launch of this Strategic Plan marks a pivotal moment in GGOS's trajectory, as we set our sights on innovation, advocacy, communication, and integration of cutting-edge technology to drive the next era of geodetic excellence.

Over the years, GGOS has stood as a clearinghouse for geodetic information expertise, providing an integrating framework for all IAG Components (Services, Commissions, Inter-Commission Committees and Projects) and acting as a central interface between science and society. With this new Strategic Plan, we seize the opportunity not only to build on our rich legacy but also to pioneer fresh initiatives that will help improve the way we perceive, measure, and understand the complex geodynamic processes of our planet.

Our Strategic Plan encompasses an ambitious vision, one that envisions a future where geodetic data is not a scientific asset only, but an essential resource guiding decision-making across diverse fields. From monitoring the Earth system and mitigating the impacts of climate change to bolstering disaster resilience and underpinning sustainable development, the power of geodetic observations and products knows no bounds.

The first goal, **Visibility and Engagement**, focuses on making geodesy more visible and engaging with various stakeholders. The aim is to raise awareness about the benefits of geodesy for science and society. This goal involves showcasing how geodesy is the only science capable of directly quantifying changes in the Earth system, and therefore, how geodetic data and products are indispensable in all global and regional initiatives to measure and mitigate the effects of global change. By doing so, GGOS aims to advocate for geodesy in major global frameworks such as the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS), the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, and the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction and to increase its recognition as a vital tool for addressing current and future scientific and societal needs.

The second goal, **Science-Policy Networking**, focuses on contributing to the sustainability of the United Nations Global Geodetic Reference Frame (UN-GGRF) through collaboration with key entities such as the UN Committee of Experts on Global Geospatial Information Management (UN-GGIM) Sub-Committee on Geodesy (SCoG) and the UN Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence (UN-GGCE). GGOS aims to demonstrate the value of geodesy through innovative applications, provide scientific advice for policy development, communicate the scientific foundation of geodesy, and facilitate the interaction of policy-makers with the geodesy community.

The third goal, **Capacity Enhancement and Sustainability**, focuses on supporting the improvement and sustainability of the global geodetic infrastructure while strengthening the capabilities of geodetic experts. GGOS aims to promote modernisation, extension, and maintenance of geodetic resources, while fostering capacity enhancement and knowledge sharing within the geodetic community. This goal also emphasises the importance of safeguarding and openly sharing geodetic Earth observations and products as essential resources.

The fourth goal, **Comprehensive and Cross-Cutting Analysis**, focuses on the core mission of using geodetic data and reference frames to monitor, map, and understand the changing Earth. To achieve this, GGOS builds on the outcomes of the other IAG Components and acts as a communication bridge with diverse communities to forge partnerships to address global challenges. The objective is to enhance the understanding and utilisation of integrated, cross-technique geodetic Earth observations, combining geodesy with other Earth observation technologies. This will support informed decision-making and policies based on data and science. The ultimate aim is to provide a comprehensive platform for geodetic analysis and information-sharing, making geodetic data and resources more visible and accessible to all.

As we commence implementation of this plan, we extend our gratitude to the collective efforts of our colleagues in the IAG and the global geodesy community. The dedication and insights from each of you have been instrumental in shaping this roadmap. Together, we will embark on a path of innovation, collaboration, and discovery, pushing the boundaries of geodetic science for a better understanding of our changing Earth.

We invite you to delve into the four goals of our new Strategic Plan, to explore the objectives that will advance geodesy and to join us in turning these aspirations into reality. The future of GGOS begins now, and with your steadfast support, there is no limit to what we can achieve together.

Laura Sánchez
GGOS President
2023 – 2027
Technische Universität München,
Deutsches Geodätisches
Forschungsinstitut, Munich, Germany

Basara Miyahara
GGOS President 2019 – 2023
Geospatial Information Authority,
Tsukuba, Japan

GGOS at a Glance

GGOS is the Global Geodetic Observing System of the International Association of Geodesy (IAG). GGOS was established with the main objective of integrating and optimising data analysis resources, procedures and dissemination of results performed by the different IAG components, namely the IAG Services, Commissions, Inter-Commission Committees (ICC) and dedicated projects.

Essentially, GGOS works with the IAG Services to provide unique, mutually consistent, and easily accessible geodetic products (including the geodetic reference frames and the gravity field models) and the relevant geodetic constants for science and society. GGOS works in concert with Commissions, ICCs and dedicated projects concerning new developments, and it keeps all IAG components informed of the work in GGOS. This interaction is essential to understand the critical components of the Earth system, and advance geodetic knowledge as well as technology development.

The societal benefit of integrated, consistent and high quality geodetic products is wide reaching, including improved navigation systems, better understanding of climate and environmental change, reliable Earth surface deformation modelling, precise monitoring of mass transport within the Earth's system, accurately determining changes in the rotation of the Earth, etc.

Motivation for the establishment of GGOS as well as its main goals and challenges were documented by the IAG science community in 2009 in The Global Geodetic Observing System: Meeting the requirements of a global society on a changing planet in 2020¹.

GGOS Vision

Advancing our understanding of the dynamic Earth system by quantifying our planet's changes in space and time.

GGOS Mission

We live on a dynamic planet in constant motion that requires long-term continuous quantification of its changes in a truly stable frame of reference, everywhere on or close to the Earth surface, at any time, and at high spatial resolution. This ambitious program requires a strong cooperation among the geodetic, geodynamic and geophysical communities, and to external stakeholders. GGOS endeavours to provide this integration at the highest level, in service to the scientific community and society as a whole.

Structure of the International Association of Geodesy

¹Plag H.-P. and Pearlman M. (Eds.) *Global Geodetic Observing System: Meeting the Requirements of a Global Society on a Changing Planet in 2020*, Springer Berlin, Heidelberg, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-02687-4>

GGOS Strategic Priorities

observations

services

products

GGOS regularly revises and updates its strategic priorities to meet emerging needs in geodesy. In the focus of GGOS are:

- The **observations** needed to monitor, map, and understand changes in the Earth's shape, rotation, and mass distribution.
- The **global geodetic frame of reference** that is the fundamental backbone for measuring and consistently interpreting key global change processes and for many other scientific and societal applications.
- The **benefit of science and society** by providing the foundation upon which advances in Earth and planetary system science and applications are built.

This new GGOS Strategic Plan is built around four Strategic Priorities that were first communicated in 2011 and then reiterated in the 2014 Strategic Plan, and continue to be relevant to the activities and future efforts of GGOS. The strategic priorities are:

- **Geodetic Information and Expertise**
Development and maintenance of organisational intangible assets, including geodetic information, expertise, and capacity building.
- **Global Geodetic Infrastructure**
Identification of gaps in the geodetic infrastructure and advocacy for modernisation, extension and maintenance of the existing global geodetic infrastructure.
- **Standardisation, Integration and Optimisation**
Interaction with all IAG components to provide unique standards and mutually consistent, highly reliable, and easily accessible geodetic products.
- **Communication, Education, and Outreach**
Public relations, marketing, outreach, and engagement to ensure a long-term sustainable geodetic enterprise.

In developing this Strategic Plan, GGOS aims to reinforce its role as a collaboration hub in the International Association of Geodesy (IAG), working as an observing system in support of sustainable geodesy by advocating and integrating diverse geodetic technologies and applications.

GGOS Strategic Planning Committee

Key drivers and Long-term goals

This new Strategic Plan is based on an extensive community survey consisting of six closed questions (multiple choice with predetermined answers) and seven SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) questions. 70 colleagues from 32 countries responded to the GGOS survey between 11 July and 30 September 2022. Based on this brainstorming, the GGOS Strategic Planning Committee convened a two-day community workshop to discuss and identify cross-cutting *community needs* that each strategic goal will seek to address. Guided by the Strategic Goals, the Community Needs are elements of a holistic effort to support the geodesy community and advance the recognition and use of geodesy for public benefit through *innovation, advocacy, communication* and *integration*.

The long-term goals focus on:

- **Visibility and engagement**
- **Science-policy networking**
- **Capacity enhancements and sustainable capabilities**
- **Comprehensive and cross-cutting analysis**

Looking forward, implementation of this plan will work toward sustainable and resilient contributions to the IAG community and its work. This plan continues in the spirit of the 2014 Strategic Plan, in that it is intended to guide GGOS as an organisation in service to the global geodesy community – as well as the growing number of people relying upon geodesy-enabled or geodesy-enhanced information in their daily lives.

Drivers

Strategic Plan Matrix

GOAL 1

Visibility and Engagement

Innovate contribution of geodesy to face emerging societal needs, Sustainable Developing Goals, Sendai Framework, Geohazards assessment, etc.

Advocate geodesy to stakeholders and society through participation in broader Earth Observation initiatives and programs

Communicate the essential role of geodesy in monitoring global change and supporting daily life applications based on positioning, navigation and timing

Integrate interdisciplinary collaborations to address major science challenges and societal relevant topics

GOAL 2

Science-Policy Networking

Innovate in the usability of novel applications showing the added value of geodesy

Advocate scientific recommendations, technical guidance, and implementation roadmaps in geodetic matters

Communicate how IAG provides scientific foundation, in complement to UN-GGCE policies

Integrate the geodesy community to policy- and decision-makers and vice versa

GOAL 3

Capacity Enhancement and Sustainability

Innovate by incubating new concepts, technologies, products and applications

Advocate for new, enhanced, updated and globally distributed ground and space-based geodetic infrastructure, alongside FAIR, TRUST and CARE data management practices

Communicate the value of state-of-the-art geodetic infrastructure for the benefit of society, science and industry, and the importance of academic education in geodesy as an avenue to excellence and sustainability

Integrate geodesists around the world wishing to collaborate on infrastructure developments, capacity, expertise, and training across IAG

GOAL 4

Comprehensive and Cross-cutting Analysis

Innovate by identifying new research fields, serving as a platform for cross-cutting expertise, and developing new approaches for consistent combination of geodetic observables

Advocate benefits of consistent and high-precise geodetic products, especially those based on multi-technique combinations and common analysis standards

Communicate with geodetic stakeholders on the needs for and benefits of geodetic space missions, new technologies and related ground infrastructure

Integrate by providing a user-friendly one-stop shop linking users to diverse IAG technical service resources and analysis-ready data (GGOS portal)

Visibility and Engagement

Raise awareness of the benefits of geodesy to society.

GOAL 1

Goal 1 focuses on appropriately increasing the visibility of geodesy as well as engagement with a diverse and expanding set of stakeholders, with the intention of raising awareness of the benefits of geodesy to society. This goal seeks to cultivate awareness, build capacity, and promote innovation to increase the visibility and recognition of geodesy's role in society. This includes utilising major diplomatic frameworks, such as the Global Earth Observation System of Systems of the Group on Earth Observations GEO, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, and others to demonstrate the contributions of geodesy to face current and emerging social needs. This provides a foundation for targeted advocacy to relevant organisations, initiatives, and programmes that include geodesy as part of a broader portfolio of Earth observations. Resources for communicating the essential role of geodesy to monitor global change and support diverse applications of positioning, navigation, and timing will be enhanced, leveraging the cross-cutting nature of UN frameworks to communicate the role and use of geodesy in the context of the most pressing issues facing global society. This will nurture strategic collaborations for interdisciplinary integration of geodesy to address novel and emerging scientific and social challenges. Cultivate awareness among stakeholders, including contributing organisations and UN bodies as well as a diverse and expanding community of intermediary- and end-users.

Objective 1.1 – Innovate contribution of geodesy to face emerging societal needs, Sustainable Developing Goals, Sendai Framework, Geohazards assessment, etc.

The United Nations has identified 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to ensure a globally homogeneous social well-being. Geodesy contributes indirectly to all SDGs that require spatially located information (geo-referenced data) for the implementation of their actions, and more directly to the SDGs on climate (13), oceans (14), terrestrial ecosystems (15), and natural hazards monitoring and disaster risk reduction (Sendai Framework). One of the current objectives of GGOS is to increase the visibility of geodesy's contribution to the successful achievement of these goals. This visibility should include not only the contribution of well-established techniques, but also technological innovations that are being developed and have a high potential to improve the monitoring of Earth system changes and their impacts. For example, spatially continuous modelling of land surface deformation using areal tracking techniques as complement to point observations; real-time monitoring of natural hazards; use of new sensors based on quantum technologies or high-precision optical clocks, etc.

Objective 1.2 – Advocate geodesy to stakeholders and society through participation in broader Earth Observation initiatives and programmes

GGOS is the contribution of the IAG to the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS). GEOSS is a set of coordinated, independent Earth observation, information and processing systems that interact and provide access to diverse information for a wide range of users in both the public and private sectors. GEOSS was established and is supported by the Group on Earth Observations (GEO). There is a need for GGOS to further disseminate the capabilities of geodesy as a science capable of directly quantifying changes in the Earth system. In this context, GGOS should seek the active participation of the geodesy community in current GEO flagships, programmes and initiatives. IAG's contribution to the evaluation and measurement of success reported by GEO on the SDGs, climate action or disaster risk reduction needs to be strengthened and made more visible. In addition, the diversity of data, models and products generated by the different IAG components should be aggregated and made available through the GEOSS portal. The GGOS portal (see Objective 4.4.) will play a key role in this respect.

Objective 1.3 – Communicate the essential role of geodesy in monitoring global change and supporting daily life applications based on positioning, navigation and timing

In today's world, where problems are global in nature and require equally global solutions based on global infrastructures, it is necessary that the contributions of geodesy are known and disseminated in such a way that all communities, developed and developing, are aware of the need to invest in and maintain a geodetic reference infrastructure as basis for a sustainable development. GGOS aims to address this issue by describing and advocating the contribution of geodesy to the Societal Benefit Areas (SBAs) outlined by GEO as the flagship for GEOSS. These areas represent the domains in which Earth observations are translated into support for political decision-making. By highlighting the contribution of geodesy to the SBAs, a direct communication channel will be built between the IAG and international initiatives working on the implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change, the UN Convention on Biological Diversity, etc.

Objective 1.4 – Integrate interdisciplinary collaborations to address major science challenges and societal relevant topics

The contribution of geodesy to Earth system monitoring is not limited only to direct measurements of Earth system changes. The increasing accuracy of geodetic measurements has forced geodesists to consider comprehensive models of the Earth for proper analysis of their geodetic measurements. This has led to a stronger interaction with related disciplines also engaged in the study of the Earth system and its components such as hydrology, oceanography, meteorology, glaciology, etc. After all, each of these sciences studies the same Earth and observes different signals of the same phenomena with different sensors, techniques and spatial and temporal resolutions. Thus, a comprehensive Earth system research cannot be carried out individually by a single discipline in isolation; but it is necessary that geodesy and its neighbouring disciplines work together and complement each other. Therefore, one of the objectives of GGOS is to promote interdisciplinary and international cooperation for the implementation of integrated methodologies covering all components of the Earth system: the atmosphere, hydrosphere, cryosphere, oceans, and solid Earth.

Science-Policy Networking

Contribute to the sustainability of the UN Global Geodetic Reference Frame (UN-GGRF) through collaboration with key UN initiatives on geodesy.

GOAL 2

Goal 2 ensures that GGOS contributes to sustaining the United Nations Global Geodetic Reference Frame (UN-GGRF) through science-policy networking in collaboration with the UN Committee of Experts on Global Geospatial Information Management (UN-GGIM) Subcommittee on Geodesy (SCoG), as well as the recently-established UN Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence (UN-GGCE). In alignment with key documents outlining the modalities of the UN-GGRF, GGOS will support innovations that demonstrate the added value of geodesy in applications based on InSAR, gravimetry, emerging technologies, etc. Innovations in handling, processing, and analysis of geodetic data – both alone and as a component of trans-disciplinary Earth observations campaigns – will be encouraged, especially in the context of utilising artificial intelligence to bridge gaps in geodetic data analysis capabilities. GGOS will assist UN-GGRF advocacy by providing scientific recommendations, technical guidance, and insight towards successful implementation of geodesy in a variety of sectors. In this way, GGOS will form a part of IAG’s contributions to the scientific guidance of the UN-GGCE, complementing the political elements and guidance from the United Nations. In this manner, a new avenue for integrating the geodesy community with policy and decision-makers will be built.

Objective 2.1 – Innovate in the usability of novel applications showing the added value of geodesy

The IAG’s greatest response to technological development has been the establishment of the IAG Scientific Services. The IAG Services collect, store and analyse geodetic data and provide openly accessible products based on best-effort practices. However, this basic geodetic infrastructure is not secure in times of reduced funding for science in general. From this point of view, a priority action is that GGOS as the IAG’s observing system continues to consolidate its position as a tool, consisting essentially of high quality services, standards and references, and theoretical and observational innovations to provide highly reliable end-user products serving to other geosciences and societal needs in general. The ultimate goal is to support the continuity of existing Services and the establishment of new ones by advocating the importance of Earth observation geodetic infrastructure as an essential resource that must be protected, made openly accessible, and integrated to provide maximum value in support of achieving national and international calls for resilient societies, sustainable economic growth, and a healthy environment worldwide.

Objective 2.2 – Advocate scientific recommendations, technical guidance, and implementation roadmaps in geodetic matters

With the UN Resolution on the UN-GGRF, the international community has recognised the need for a sustained and integrated portfolio of geodetic resources that ensure the framework of reference for the determination and appropriate interpretation of geo-referenced information critical to understanding the causes and consequences of global change, as well as for developing strategies to mitigate its effects. This requires the identification of fundamental research and operational objectives based on Earth system monitoring using geodetic observing systems, sensors, networks, models, databases, and products. The expertise of the IAG is a guarantee to support decision-making processes and is essential to outline objectives, define implementation strategies, and establish a hierarchical framework of priorities in the deployment, employment, and sustainment of the UN-GGRF. In this context, GGOS, in collaboration with the other components of the IAG, is called upon to develop the technical documentation necessary to support an informed decision-making so that available resources are used efficiently and optimally to promote the establishment and long-term sustainability of the UN-GGRF.

Objective 2.3 – Communicate how IAG provides scientific foundation, in complement to UN-GGCE policies

The primary objective of the UN Resolution on the UN-GGRF is to coordinate internationally the efforts of UN Member States to maintain and improve the global geodetic infrastructure and the sustainable use of the data. The success of this initiative is only possible if the political actions are based on scientific criteria and well-coordinated international efforts. It is not enough to extend the geodetic infrastructure without ensuring global distribution, technological innovation and capacity development to collect, analyse and deliver geodetic data and products. The IAG and its components have the necessary expertise to identify the strategic locations where new geodetic observatories are needed, what technological improvements are required to avoid the obsolescence of the existing infrastructure, and to support the education and training of specialised staff for the proper collection and analysis of the measurements. In this context, GGOS seeks a symbiosis between the scientific expertise of the IAG and the political framework of the UN-GGCE in order to optimise resources for an effective improvement of the global geodetic infrastructure.

Objective 2.4 – Integrate the geodesy community to policy- and decision-makers and vice versa

In general, the international community uses geodetic products in a wide range of applications without realising that behind each product there is an extensive observation and data analysis infrastructure. The IAG Services provide their products free of charge and all efforts to maintain and improve the geodetic infrastructure of reference are invisible to the user community. One of the goals of GGOS is to make the general public, policy makers and the media aware of the societal importance of geodesy. In a joint effort with UN-GGCE, GGOS aims to make policy and decision makers understand that geodesy is a strategic area for economic, social and welfare development and long-term stability in every region of the world. The aim is to provide geodetic data, information, and knowledge that will enable stakeholders to improve decision-making processes and inform policy requirements, promote the exchange of best practices, enable the updating of new technologies, and create new economic opportunities.

Capacity Enhancement and Sustainability

Strengthen sustainable geodetic capabilities: measuring facilities, data analysis, geodetic methods, and expertise.

Goal 3 seeks to promote the modernisation, extension and maintenance of the global geodetic infrastructure and to strengthen sustainable geodetic capabilities through capacity enhancement and knowledge sharing. GGOS advocacy for geodetic capacity development will address pressing needs in ground and space infrastructure, especially in the case of degrading or missing infrastructure as well as the networking and expertise necessary to utilise and maintain the UN-GGRF. GGOS will support innovations in geodetic concepts, technologies, products, and applications by acting as an incubator to nascent initiatives within the IAG community. GGOS will advocate data sharing initiatives such as FAIR, TRUST and CARE as well as raise awareness for the potential impacts of radio-frequency interference. Efforts to communicate how geodesy is used in space missions, as well as how state-of-the-art geodetic infrastructure positively impacts science, industry, and social well-being will further support this goal. Furthermore, human capacity development will be integrated with infrastructural development, to ensure that geodesists around the world wishing to collaborate can gain access to expertise and training within the IAG community.

Objective 3.1 – Innovate by incubating new concepts, technologies, products and applications

Currently, the IAG and its components are confronted daily with the vast amount of data generated by terrestrial and space-based techniques, which has meant that geodesists must also be aware of the evolving technologies for data management and product dissemination. In the immediate future, it will be necessary to initiate actions to adapt technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, Virtual Reality, Internet of Things, Machine Learning or Cloud Computing to the needs of geodesy. While these technologies make it possible to analyse and use data effectively, it is necessary to ensure that the results are consistent with the principles of the physical sciences that explain changes in the Earth system. Therefore, analysis methodologies must evolve in parallel with data technologies; otherwise, the geodetic products would not be interpretable and would contribute little to modelling and prediction of global change and its effects. The incubation of new concepts, technologies, products and applications is closely related to the establishment of new GGOS Focus Areas (see Objective 4.1).

Objective 3.2 – Advocate for new, enhanced, updated and globally distributed ground and space-based geodetic infrastructure, alongside FAIR, TRUST and CARE data management practices

GGOS's promotion of geodetic capacity development will tackle urgent requirements for ground and space infrastructure, particularly in the event of deteriorating or absent infrastructure. The proliferation of satellites is driven by space agencies, government agencies, or private companies, and in many cases geodesists have access to intermediate products rather than direct observations. This contributes to some uncertainty in the content and quality of the data that can be used for geodetic purposes, since the intermediate steps between the measurement and the product delivered by the satellite mission owner are not known. From this perspective, a further objective of GGOS is to advocate for a consistent and well-documented data processing chain that describes how the original observational data are transformed into user-relevant information. This should include processing standards, consistent metadata, uncertainty and quality attributes, description of final products, and user-friendly tools to enable end-users to access these products quickly, reliably and securely. In particular, GGOS promotes the use of the FAIR, TRUST and CARE data management practices.

Objective 3.3 – Communicate the value of state-of-the-art geodetic infrastructure for the benefit of society, science and industry, and the importance of education in geodesy as an avenue to excellence and sustainability

Deterioration of geodetic infrastructure frequently results in reduced efficiency and accuracy, causing service disruptions and higher maintenance expenses. Modern geodetic technology, particularly space-based approaches, occupies a pivotal position in the establishment of accurate global geodetic reference frames. These are, in turn, critical for monitoring the Earth's dynamic processes. GGOS aims to communicate the importance of cutting-edge geodetic infrastructure, globally distributed, in modern society. It enables accurate navigation, facilitates emergency response, supports Earth system research, and drives innovation across various industries. However, relying solely on technological advancements falls short. Human resources proficient in addressing critical challenges related to the analysis and interpretation of geodetic data are indispensable. Unfortunately, in recent decades, a significant decline in enrolment in geodetic academic programmes has been observed. Therefore, it is imperative to promote the study of geodesy to guarantee geodetic excellence and sustainability in the future. It is important to convey to younger generations that a robust academic foundation in geodesy facilitates access to a range of career prospects, such as roles in academia, government agencies, private industry, and research institutions.

Objective 3.4 – Integrate geodesists around the world wishing to collaborate on infrastructure developments, capacity, expertise, and training across IAG

The IAG and UN initiatives regarding geodesy promote the development of a globally distributed geodetic infrastructure. Achieving an understanding, appropriate management, and effective utilisation of modern geodetic technologies necessitates a diverse approach that integrates education, infrastructure development, policy advocacy, and international collaboration. In several capacities, IAG functions as a focal point for geodesists worldwide, facilitating cooperation, information-sharing, and capacity enhancement. However, the significant disparity in geodetic matters between the global South and North remains. GGOS aims to support the formulation of geodetic training programmes by compiling a thorough catalogue of existing capacity building initiatives within the IAG and identifying new areas for knowledge transfer. Additionally, outreach activities will be conducted to promote participation in various components of the IAG, particularly to aspiring young scientists and geodesists from less developed countries.

Comprehensive and cross-cutting analysis

Engage across geodetic techniques for integrated geodetic research and technological developments.

GOAL 4

Goal 4 addresses the core of the GGOS mission, supporting geodetic data and reference frames to monitor, map, and understand our changing planet. In implementation of this goal's objectives, GGOS will engage with stakeholder communities and foster strategic partnerships to address global and regional challenges, by increasing the understanding and use of integrated, cross-technique geodetic Earth observations, along with novel combinations of geodesy and other Earth observation technologies to support science-based and data-driven decision and policy-making. Innovative research utilising high-precision geodetic products – especially those based on a combination of techniques and common analysis standards, will continue being promoted and incubated. GGOS will reach out to space agencies and other government entities responsible for national geodesy programs to collaborate on improved communication of the needs and benefits of geodetic space missions, and how geodetic infrastructure and knowledge contributes to new technologies. Finally, GGOS will enable improved awareness and access to diverse technical resources throughout the IAG by providing a comprehensive referral resource (a *one-stop shop*) for individuals and organisations searching for geodetic data and capacity development resources.

Objective 4.1 – Innovate by identifying new research fields, serving as a platform for cross-cutting expertise, and developing new approaches for consistent combination of geodetic observables

In order to fully benefit from the breath-taking technological developments in sensor systems and observation techniques in geodesy over the last years, a parallel and consistent further development of geodetic analysis and combination methods is required, taking into account cross-cutting expertise by using advanced geophysical modelling results, area observation methods and new observation concepts (e.g. SAR/InSAR, GNSS reflectometry, optical clocks) as well as the application of data assimilation and deep learning methods. To this end, innovative approaches will be developed by identifying new research areas and creating new GGOS Focus Areas as cross-disciplinary units to work towards future integrated products needed for a better understanding of our dynamic planet, including natural hazards, disaster risk reduction, and many other challenges of our modern society.

Objective 4.2 – Advocate benefits of consistent and high-precise geodetic products, especially those based on multi-technique combinations and common analysis standards

A key objective of GGOS is the integrated analysis of the Earth's geometry, rotation and gravity field to provide consistent geodetic products. To this end, it is essential that data analysis is based on the definition and application of common standards, conventions and consistent representation and parameterisation of the relevant quantities. Despite the high importance of geodetic products for many tasks of the modern society, geodesy and the economic benefits of its freely and openly available products are not well known to the general public and policy makers. One aim of GGOS is therefore to promote the key role of geodetic products as fundamental contributions to solving societal challenges related to climate change impacts and mitigation, the operation of early warning systems, as well as the management of infrastructure, resources and everyday life applications.

Objective 4.3 – Communicate with geodetic stakeholders on the needs for and benefits of geodetic space missions, new technologies and related ground infrastructure

GGOS recognises the need to communicate with geodetic stakeholders (space agencies, national mapping and surveying authorities and other organisations responsible for geodesy) about the importance of a well-distributed global network of geodetic observatories and stations, space-based infrastructure including space co-locations (e.g. GENESIS) and dedicated gravity field satellite missions (e.g. GRACE Follow-On, MAGIC) as a fundamental basis for the production of high accuracy geodetic products. The economic value of geodetic products for a better understanding of the Earth system and the causes and effects of global change phenomena, as well as for a wide range of positioning and navigation applications, will be highlighted. In addition, simulations of ground network geometry (new stations, co-locations), new observation concepts (e.g. inter-satellite links) and the development of methods for the optimal use of satellite co-locations are essential to define future concepts and communicate them to stakeholders.

Objective 4.4 – Integrate by providing a user-friendly one-stop shop linking users to diverse IAG technical service resources and analysis-ready data (GGOS portal)

The IAG Services provide a variety of important and valuable geodetic data, information, and products that are increasingly relevant for Earth system research, geospatial data management and sustainable development. Currently, it is difficult for many people to obtain an overview of all available geodetic data and products. The objective of GGOS is to fill this gap by developing the GGOS portal, which should serve as a unique search and access point (one-stop shop) for geodetic data and products. These data products should be described by detailed metadata and remain physically located at their originating data centres. The GGOS portal will ensure a better discoverability, user-friendly interfaces, easy-to-understand descriptions of products and observation techniques, and a comprehensive catalogue of geodetic data sources. With this platform, GGOS will contribute to increasing the visibility of geodetic data for scientific research and to raising awareness of geodesy and its useful products to other disciplines and to society.

Strategic Plan Implementation

This document outlines the aims and objectives of the GGOS Strategic Plan 2023 – 2033. The accompanying Implementation Plan, detailed separately, outlines the steps required to achieve these goals. The Implementation Plan focuses on identifying, assigning, executing, and monitoring progress, with some actions requiring multi-year efforts. GGOS will periodically assess progress towards achieving this plan and provide updates to the geodesy community.